

International research trials that aim to tackle critical global health issues, such as iron deficiency among women, make the greatest impact when both the intervention being trialled and its implementation can be **sustained long-term and adapted and scaled in different contexts**. Two key elements that can support sustainability and translatability include plans and people: 1. integrating **plans** into trial designs to capture and report data that can inform translation within and across settings facing similar health issues; 2. empowering **people** to champion the work, build their capacity and the capacity of other implementers and interest-holders, through knowledge sharing. To inform future trials and health programmes, we surveyed interest-holders committed to advancing women’s health and developing sustainable solutions to tackle iron deficiency and poor nutrition. The **purpose** of this knowledge mobilisation activity is to report insights on best practices and factors influencing sustainability and translatability of research to other contexts.

Sample	Experts-by-experience: researchers, graduate students, NGO project managers, youth & community health advocates, economists, and industry impact directors
Phenomenon of interest	Insights and perspectives on approaches and strategies to support the translatability of trial results
Design	Structured survey informed by academic literature and insights from the Alliance Against Iron Deficiency working group to ensure rigor and relevance of the survey questions
Evaluation	Qualitative thematic analysis of surveys to uncover key themes and practical recommendations
Research type	Qualitative, focused on exploring applied and experiential knowledge of experts-by-experience
Outcome	Inform effective planning of community-based research trials and health programmes to ensure sustainability and translatability of findings to other contexts facing similar global health issues

Emerging insights

Impactful and sustainable trial designs consider how results can be translated and scaled other contexts. This requires careful planning and capacity building both during and after the trial to support knowledge synthesis and sharing.

Implementing trialled interventions and key findings into other contexts

Strategies to consider incorporating into trial designs, to support translation of findings to other contexts:

Identify, map, and report communities' contextual factors

to help implementers identify shared or different physical, cultural, and gender-based characteristics, barriers, and facilitators influencing implementation/intervention success, and how applicable the findings are to new communities of interest.

Co-define and report core and adaptable elements of implementation approaches and interventions

This approach can guide implementers on what is key to the success of the intervention, and what needs to be adapted for other communities. Core elements may be related to dosage and adherence, and adaptable elements may be related to the needs of communities.

Use a standardised framework to report implementation and/or intervention details

Details should include actors, audience, action targets, implementation strategies, core and adaptable elements. This framework can be used as a guide for other implementers.

Knowledge sharing recommendations:

Empower local champions

Establish a core group of knowledge brokers to share key findings, engage implementers and other interest-holders, and champion implementation in other contexts.

Create knowledge products

Develop accessible summaries, guides, and evidence reports to inform implementation and influence buy-in and uptake.

Establish knowledge sharing forums

Use locally led workshops, webinars, and digital tools to engage and strengthen learning across implementers and other interest-holders.

★ **Key considerations:** knowledge sharing approaches are most effective when adapted to interest-holders’ needs

Key people to support knowledge sharing within and across communities/settings:

Local NGOs

Community leaders

Implementation experts

Government ministries

★ **Key considerations:** Engaging local champions and interest-holders can secure buy-in and support sustainability